

BiMeGaFuel

Newsletter

 Ed. 2 – Feb 2026

**Bio Methanol Production via
Chemical Looping Gasification
Coupled with Membrane Reactors**

Project number: 101147737
Coordinator: Research Institute of Sweden
Project Coordinator: Amir Soleimani Salim
Duration: 2024-2028
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Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-07

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www.biomegafuelproject.eu

WELCOME

- **Welcome to our second Newsletter!**

This edition feature some of the latest news and interview with our partners.

On our website www.biomegafuelproject.eu you will find public presentations, all the public deliverables of the project and many other interesting news. Please follow us!

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Interview with our partner

Few months ago, we had the chance to visit our partner, GIDARA Energy B.V, in their office located in Schiphol, Amsterdam, for an in-depth interview about their work on the Bio-MeGaFuel Project.

Huge thanks to GIDARA Energy B.V. for the engaging conversation and warm hospitality.

Interview with our partner

Could you please introduce GIDARA?

GIDARA Energy b.v. is a leading waste to value company. Using our High Temperature Winkler (HTW[®]) gasification technology, we convert biomass and waste to renewable or sustainable fuels and chemicals. We align well with our partners in trying to decarbonize hard-to-abate sectors.

Avishek Goel
Head of Technology Development

Over the years, GIDARA Energy B.V. has performed several pilot scale HTW[®] gasification test campaigns at the Technical University of Darmstadt to explore different feedstocks. The ability to perform HTW[®] test campaigns at TU Darmstadt offers a unique opportunity to benchmark new technologies like Chemical Looping Gasification (CLG) against a mature and proven technology like HTW[®].

TU Darmstadt pilot plant facilities

Interview with our partner

Could you please introduce GIDARA's task in the project?

We were responsible for the task of sourcing and selecting feedstocks for the project.

If we look at the whole process, we look at it in two blocks. For the upstream process, we put the waste feedstock or biomass feedstock into the gasifier, and we get syngas. For the downstream block, we use the syngas in the methanol synthesis reactors that TU Eindhoven is working at on to get biomethanol.

So for the upstream process (gasification), for both HTW® as well as chemical looping, there are certain physical and chemical parameters for the feedstock to be able to fit the process. It took a bit of time and effort, but it was a very interesting task as it gave us a lot of insight and knowledge on potentially new European biomass feedstocks that may be applicable.

Nivya Uday Kodimaniyanda
Technology Development Engineer

Feedstock samples in the
ECOMONDO showcase

Interview with our partner

What kind of feedstocks can be processed in the HTW® gasifier?

Avikar Saberwal
Technology Development Engineer

We are mainly focused on three different categories of feedstock to process in our HTW® gasifier.

The first one is biomass waste, which is mainly concentrated biogenic content. The second one is mixed waste. It is a combination of biogenic waste and also municipal solid waste driven RDF, which is the non-recyclable fraction of the waste itself. And the third one is recycled carbon, which is derived from fossil-based sources.

Examples of feedstocks to process in the HTW® gasifier

Highlights & Updates

Feb 2025

M6 General Assembly meeting at
GIDARA Energy B.V., the Netherlands

Apr 2025

Francisco Garcia in the 25th International
Conference on Fluidized Bed Conversion in
Nanjing, China

May 2025

Visit in GIDARA Energy B.V.

Sep 2025

Virtual Tech Forum

Highlights & Updates

Sep 2025

Bio-MeGaFuel formed partnership with Flexby project

Oct 2025

16 Oct, M12 GA meeting at CSIC, Zaragoza, Spain

19 – 22 Oct, CSIC participated at the "XVII Reunión del Grupo Español del Carbón "

21 – 23 Oct, Project coordinator presented at SepTech conference, Eindhoven

Highlights & Updates

For more details on the events and highlights, please visit our project website

www.biomegafuelproject.eu

Nov 2025

4 – 7 Nov, ECOMONDO showcase in Rimini, Italy

26 – 27 Nov, International workshop on Sustainable & Circular Technologies, Eindhoven
This workshop is co-hosted by Bio-MeGaFuel and other 12 EU projects.

Upcoming events

www.biomegafuelproject.eu

26th January

Webinar Chemical Looping Process
(online-Teams)

24th Febuary

4th General Assembly Meeting
1 CUBE, The Netherlands

25th - 26th Febuary

Winter School "Gasification & Membrane Reactors"
Eindhoven, The Netherlands

28th - 29th May

Symposium "Integrating Waste-to-fuel Innovations for Hard-to-Abate Sectors", Barcelona, Spain

31st Aug - 4th Sep

International Conference on Chemical Looping ICCL 2026
Manchester, United Kingdom

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BiMeGaFuel

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